
Advancing Fistula Thrombectomy: The Role of Central Venous Access

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Abstract

Central Venous Access (CVA) has progressively emerged as a viable alternative to conventional direct access methods in the domain of fistula thrombectomy. This access methodology offers a potential alternative to direct fistula and graft puncture, enhancing the procedural dynamics and possibly mitigating some associated complications and device limitations. The ensuing article explores the possible advantages and alternative applications of employing Central Venous Access in fistula thrombectomy procedures. The deliberation underscores the criticality of access site selection, the ensuing flow dynamics, possible implications on infection rates, and the opportunistic utilization of larger bore thrombectomy devices.

Keywords

Central Vein, Arterial Venous Fistula, Arterial Venous Graft, Hemodialysis Access, Jugular Vein, Thrombectomy

Introduction

Introduction:

In the ambit of vascular access maintenance for hemodialysis, fistula thrombectomy stands as a prevalent and necessary procedure to ensure the patency and functionality of arteriovenous fistulas and grafts.^[1] Traditionally, the direct access to fistulas and grafts has been the cornerstone of such interventions. However, the application of Central Venous Access (CVA), typically via the internal jugular or femoral vein, presents a compelling narrative of possibly superior procedural and post-procedural outcomes.^[2] This narrative explores the breadth and scope of employing CVA in fistula thrombectomy, delving into the comparative merits and potential alternative applications.

Access Parameters:

The pivotal role of access site selection in fistula thrombectomy cannot be overstated. Central Venous Access, by virtue of its anatomical and physiological attributes, offers a streamlined route to the central circulation^[3], thereby potentially enhancing the maneuverability and efficacy of thrombectomy devices. The discourse elaborates on the technical and clinical parameters influencing access selection and the consequential impact on procedural outcomes.

Advantages of Central Venous Access:

Possible Reduced Infection Rates: The propensity for infections is a notable concern in direct access methods given the distal/ superficial nature of fistulas and grafts.

The proximal positioning of Central Venous Access could ostensibly ameliorate infection rates, thereby improving the overall procedural safety profile.^[1] Enhanced Flow

Dynamics: The flow dynamics inherent to the Central Venous Access potentially foster a more controlled and predictable procedural environment. The discourse delves into the comparative flow dynamics and the resultant impact on thrombectomy efficacy. Utilization of Larger Bore Thrombectomy Devices: The anatomical expanse of

central veins accords the feasibility of employing larger bore thrombectomy devices. This aspect is particularly salient as it may significantly augment clot removal efficiency, thereby enhancing the success rates of thrombectomy procedures.

Vascular access maintenance is a critical component in the management of patients requiring hemodialysis.^[2] Among the various procedures integral to ensuring robust vascular access, fistula thrombectomy is pivotal in maintaining the patency and functionality of arteriovenous fistulas and grafts. Historically, direct access to fistulas and grafts has been the conventional approach adopted by clinicians. This method, although established, presents certain challenges that may affect procedural and post-procedural outcomes such as graft infections, acute angulations, difficult access due to thrombus burdens in aneurysmal sections, and limitations in access size due to the arterialized nature of the fistulized circuit.^[1]

The utilization of Central Venous Access (CVA), typically attained via the internal jugular vein or femoral vein, offers a potential alternative to the traditional approach. The utilization of CVA could possibly mitigate some of the challenges associated with direct access methods, thus paving the way for enhanced procedural outcomes. The adoption of this method suggests a shift in clinical practice, aligning with the broader objective of optimizing patient care in hemodialysis settings.

This narrative aims to thoroughly examine the application of CVA in fistula thrombectomy, focusing on the comparative advantages it may offer over direct access methods. It also

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seeks to explore the potential alternative applications of CVA, which could further broaden its utility in vascular access maintenance. The discussion will delve into technical considerations, procedural efficacy, and the potential impact on infection rates among other pertinent factors.

The exploration of CVA in the context of fistula thrombectomy is not merely an academic exercise, but a concerted effort to possibly enhance clinical practice. By scrutinizing the merits and potential applications of CVA, this discourse contributes to a growing body of knowledge aimed at improving patient outcomes in hemodialysis. Through examination of existing practices and a thoughtful consideration of alternative approaches, the interventional procedural community continues to stride towards optimized vascular access management for hemodialysis patients.

Access Parameters:

The selection of an access site forms the cornerstone for the successful execution and outcomes of a fistula thrombectomy procedure.^[1] This choice significantly impacts the procedural ease, associated risks, and overall patient safety. The traditional approach of direct access to fistulas and grafts, employing single or dual sheath methods, has been a standard practice but is not devoid of limitations. These limitations predominantly revolve around the size of sheaths that can be utilized and the challenges inherent to the arterialized circuit.

Direct Fistula and Graft Access:

The conventional method of direct access to fistulas and grafts has primarily hinged on the utilization of single or dual sheath methods.^[1] These sheaths act as conduits for the insertion and maneuverability of thrombectomy devices, facilitating the thrombectomy process. The dual sheath method is often favored as it allows for a distinct inflow and outflow, thereby augmenting the efficiency of the thrombectomy process.

Sheath Size Limitations:

A limitation in direct access methods arises from the constraints on sheath size, often denoted in French size, which can be utilized for the procedure^[1]. The diameter of the arterialized vessels dictates the maximum size of the sheath that can be employed, thereby also restricting the size and type of thrombectomy devices that can be used. This size limitation may impede effective clot removal, possibly necessitating multiple attempts or prolonging the procedure duration. The consequence of this limitation extends beyond procedural duration; it may also affect the overall success rate of restoring vascular access patency.

Arterialized Circuit Challenges:

The arterialized circuit's high-pressure nature presents another significant challenge in direct access methods. The high-pressure environment augments the risk of bleeding during and post-procedure^[1]. Any inadvertent vessel injury or inadequate hemostasis can precipitate significant bleeding, which not only extends the patient's

recovery period but can also lead to additional complications such as hematoma formation, infection, or even loss of vascular access. Furthermore, the arterialized circuit's high flow rates may pose challenges in controlling the thrombectomy device, potentially impacting the efficiency and safety of clot removal.

The bleeding risk is not a standalone concern; it intertwines with other procedural aspects. For instance, the necessity for anticoagulation during the procedure to prevent further clot formation further compounds the bleeding risk. Moreover, the arterialized circuit's high-pressure nature may necessitate more rigorous hemostasis measures post-procedure, potentially leading to longer procedural and recovery times.

In summary, while the direct access method for fistula thrombectomy has been a longstanding practice, its limitations, particularly concerning sheath size and the challenges posed by the arterialized circuit, underscore the necessity for exploring alternative access methods. The aim is to enhance procedural outcomes, minimize associated risks, and ultimately improve the quality of care for patients requiring hemodialysis.

Advantages of Central Venous Access:

Central Venous Access (CVA) via the jugular route may present a host of advantages that potentially address the limitations inherent in direct fistula and graft access. The merits of CVA may extend to reduced infection rates, enhanced flow dynamics, and the utilization of larger bore thrombectomy devices, each of which contributes to the broader objective of optimizing procedural outcomes in fistula thrombectomy.

Reduced Infection Rates: The infection rate is a critical parameter in the evaluation of procedural success and post-procedural recovery. Fistulas and grafts, by virtue of their distal location and superficial location, are predisposed to higher infection rates.^[1] The skin and subcutaneous tissue at these sites often harbor a higher bacterial load, and the repeated needle punctures for hemodialysis access further exacerbate this risk.

Central venous access, particularly via the jugular route, being more proximal and located in a region with a typically lower bacterial load, presents a lower risk profile for infections.^[2] Additionally, the jugular route for CVA minimizes the need for multiple punctures to place dual sheaths, further mitigating the risk of infection. The proximal nature of CVA may facilitate easier maintenance of aseptic technique during procedure, which is paramount in reducing infection rates.

Enhanced Flow Dynamics: The flow dynamics within the vascular system significantly influence the ease and safety of thrombectomy procedures. CVA, by virtue of its location within the low flow venous system proximal to the arterialized section, offers a more controlled procedural environment. The predictable flow dynamics in the central venous system potentially allow for better control of thrombectomy devices, which is conducive to effective thrombectomy.

The jugular access provides a direct route to the central venous system, minimizing the tortuosity often encountered

in peripheral vascular access. This straighter path is likely to reduce the risk of catheter and device entanglement, thereby enhancing procedural safety and efficacy when having to treat large volume thrombosis due to central venous stenosis and strictures^[3]

Utilization of Larger Bore Thrombectomy Devices: The anatomy of central veins, accessible via the jugular route, permits the utilization of larger bore thrombectomy devices. This advantage is particularly salient in cases of aneurysmal thrombosed fistulas where efficient clot removal is imperative for restoring vascular access patency. Larger bore devices facilitate better thrombus resolution, and the ability to aspirate thrombus material reduces the risk of embolization, a significant concern in thrombectomy procedures.

The usage of larger bore aspiration devices becomes a viable option particularly when dealing with more subacute thrombus through the softer portion of the thrombus cap. The larger bore devices, through a single access point in the low-flow jugular, can potentially breach more subacute thrombus effectively, enhancing the thoroughness of thrombus removal while minimizing embolic risk.

Moreover, the single sheath access via the jugular as opposed to multiple sheath access in direct methods, simplifies the procedural approach, potentially reducing the procedural time and associated complications. Single access from the central venous may also facilitate control of the outflow of the vein allowing for guarded thrombectomy with utilization of novel embolic protective devices or balloon obturation to facilitate minimization of large embolic transit of thrombus to the pulmonary artery.

Routes to Fistula from the Jugular:/Femoral:

The jugular access offers a relatively straightforward route to reach common arm fistula sites. From the jugular/femoral vein, thrombectomy devices can be navigated through the central venous system, down the superior vena cava, and into the subclavian vein to reach arm fistulas. This route minimizes the number of turns and the degree of tortuosity, which is advantageous for maintaining control of thrombectomy devices and minimizing the risk of vessel injury. The anatomical proximity and directness of this route also potentially reduce the procedural time, further contributing to the overall safety and efficacy of fistula thrombectomy via central venous access.

Comparative Analysis:

Central venous access and direct access to fistulas and grafts are the primary routes employed in fistula thrombectomy procedures, each presenting unique advantages and challenges. The comparative evaluation between these access methodologies pivots around several critical parameters including infection rates, flow dynamics, and the feasibility of employing larger bore thrombectomy devices, all of which significantly influence procedural outcomes and post-procedural recovery.

Pressure Dynamics: The pressure dynamics within the vascular system are a fundamental aspect that influences the ease and efficacy of thrombectomy procedures. The average pressures within the central veins, accessible via the jugular route, range between 8 to 12 mmHg^[4]. In contrast, arteriovenous fistulas, particularly when thrombosed, exhibit significantly higher venous pressures, with

readings reported as high as 102.6 mmHg in some cases.^[5] This substantial pressure differential impacts several procedural and post-procedural parameters: Hemostasis and Hematomas: Elevated pressures in arterialized fistulas augment the risk of post-procedural bleeding and hematomas following sheath removal in percutaneous access procedures. These hematomas can manifest symptoms like pain, focal mass, and a drop in hematocrit. In severe instances, hematomas might lead to vascular occlusion, impeding the blood flow through the fistula or graft. Furthermore, severe hematomas could precipitate compartment syndrome, a condition characterized by increased pressure within the muscles which can lead to muscle and nerve damage and issues with blood flow. The timely identification and management of hematomas are crucial to prevent these serious complications and ensure the patency and functionality of the vascular access.

- **Procedural Control:** The lower pressures within the central venous system facilitate better control over thrombectomy devices, minimizing the risk of procedural complications such as vessel injury and embolization as well as faster hemostasis as opposed to the arterialized pressures in the fistula and graft.

Infection Rates: The distal nature of fistulas and grafts, coupled with the high-pressure arterialized circuit, potentially exacerbates the risk of infection, particularly in the presence of multiple punctures over time. In contrast, the proximal nature of CVA via the jugular route presents a lower bacterial load area, which may minimize the risk of infection.^[6] **Utilization of Larger Bore Thrombectomy Devices:** The anatomy of central veins permits the utilization of larger bore thrombectomy devices, which is particularly advantageous in cases of aneurysmal thrombosed fistulas. The larger bore devices facilitate efficient clot removal, and the ability to aspirate thrombus material reduces the risk of embolization. **Comparative Outcomes:** The overall complication rates concerning bleeding, hematoma, and blood dyscrasias were reported around 6% in thrombectomy procedures.^[7] The nature of access - whether central or direct - significantly influences these outcomes. The lower pressures and more controlled procedural environment associated with CVA potentially translate to lower complication rates and better procedural outcomes.

Hematoma Incidence in Direct Fistula/Graft Access:

A review involving 109 patients delineated a pronounced complication rate of 21% associated with axillary or brachial access, encompassing hematoma formation as a notable adversarial event. Specifically, the rate of major complications stood at 8.3% for surgical cutdown via the brachial artery and 13.7% for percutaneous access.^[8]

Hematoma Incidence in Central Venous Access (Jugular Vein):

While precise hematoma rates post-CVA thrombectomy remain elusive, general insights from central venous catheterization practices may shed light on the relative risk. An illustrative multicenter trial investigating nontunneled central venous catheterization across different veins reported on the incidence of hematoma, among other complications, although the precise rates were not detailed. Other sources hint at a lower rate of hematoma formation in jugular vein

access, with one study documenting around 5% hematoma rate associated with central line accesses, albeit the specific context differed from thrombectomy scenarios.^[1]

Discussion:

The exploration of Central Venous Access (CVA) in the realm of fistula thrombectomy opens a opportunities to enhance vascular access maintenance for hemodialysis, potentially addressing some of the prevailing challenges inherent in the traditional direct access methods. The putative benefits span reduced infection rates, enhanced flow dynamics, and the utilization of larger bore thrombectomy devices, each harboring the potential to significantly ameliorate procedural outcomes and patient safety.

Infection Rates Reduction: The prospect of reducing graft infection rates through CVA is a compelling one. The proximal nature of CVA, coupled with a lesser bacterial load compared to distal fistula or graft sites, lays a plausible foundation for this hypothesis. Preliminary data veer towards a positive correlation between CVA and lower infection rates. However, the substantiation of this correlation necessitates more rigorous and comprehensive research endeavors. The delineation of infection rates, segmented by access routes, and the subsequent impact on patient outcomes could significantly inform clinical practice, fostering a more evidence-based approach to vascular access in fistula thrombectomy.

Utilization of Larger Bore Thrombectomy Devices: The low flow venous system proximal to the arterialized section, accessible via jugular access, provides a conducive environment for the utilization of larger bore thrombectomy devices. Devices like the Penumbra Lightning 12 and Inari, by virtue of their design, offer a promising avenue for efficient thrombus removal. The larger bore facilitates a higher aspiration capacity, potentially translating to shorter procedure times and higher success rates in restoring vascular access patency.

Additionally, the Cleaner Thrombectomy Device from Argon Medical Devices Inc., especially when employed in conjunction with balloon occlusion or a large bore aspiration sheath, presents a novel approach to thrombus management. This amalgamated strategy could potentially enhance thrombus maceration and removal efficacy, minimizing the risk of residual thrombus and subsequent re-thrombosis while reducing the risk of central venous embolization.

Flow Dynamics and Embolization Control: The approach from the central venous system down distal to the fistula augments the control over embolization. The lower pressures and more predictable flow dynamics within the central venous system, as opposed to the high-pressure arterialized circuit, are likely to reduce the risk of disrupting the arterial plug. This, in turn, fosters a controlled environment for thrombus maceration or removal, thereby minimizing the risk of embolization. The restoration of fistula flow prior to adequate thrombus maceration or removal is a critical aspect that can significantly influence the overall success of the thrombectomy procedure.

Moreover, the potential to better control embolization, particularly in the presence of a well-seated arterial plug, underlines the potential merits of CVA in enhancing the

safety profile of fistula thrombectomy procedures via one access approach.

Conclusion:

The discussion around the potential merits of central venous access in fistula thrombectomy is burgeoning, yet still nascent. The preliminary insights, while promising, underscore the imperative for more robust research to thoroughly define the comparative benefits and risks associated with CVA versus traditional direct access methods. The exploration of such research endeavors could significantly impact clinical practice, fostering enhanced procedural outcomes, and ultimately, better quality of care for patients requiring hemodialysis.

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Figure 1. Femoral Access for Graft Thrombectomy

Figure 2. Thrombosed Graft

Figure 3. In- Stent Thrombosis

Figure 4. 135cm Cleaner XT Rotational Thrombectomy Device by Argon Medical Devices Inc. in Stent Treating Thrombus Burden

Figure 5. Complete Restoration of Graft Patency